

CURING TIME-ENERGY OPTIMIZATION OF FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION OF FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Frontal ring-opening metathesis polymerization (FROMP) is a promising thermoset composite curing process for thermoset composites, enabling rapid and energy-efficient manufacturing through a self-energized exothermic reaction. Once initiated, the polymerization front spatially propagates through the resin matrix. Among various frontal polymerization curing strategies, through-thickness curing offers potential for scalable carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite fabrication. However, manufacturing large composite structures via through-thickness curing requires the analysis of the trade-offs among curing energy and speed, as well as new strategies for scaling up the equipment and tooling required for the heating and pressure applications. To address this issue, incremental curing methods use a fixed area tool for applying pressure and heat to initiate a through-thickness front, followed by removing the pressure and feeding the composite forward to cure the following section of the composite. This process must be optimized to maintain high cure quality while minimizing energy input to fabricate large composite structures. In this study, we develop a computational and experimental approach to optimize and validate the thermal management of incremental through-thickness FROMP for CFRP. A one-dimensional reaction-diffusion model including cure kinetics is implemented to simulate the thermal and chemical reaction with different heating profiles. Using this simple model, parametric optimization with different FROMP initiation parameters is applied to find optimal thermal management cycles to reduce energy and curing time simultaneously. In addition, the simulations consider the influence of adjacent preheated domains from previous cycles to reflect thermal conditions. Experimental validation confirms that the derived optimized curing cycles produce fully cured composite segments with consistent glass transition temperatures by the dynamic mechanical analysis, comparable to those from conventional high-energy processes. The work demonstrates the feasibility of the scalable and low-cost CFRP manufacturing via incremental through-thickness FROMP, supporting the application of future large composite structure manufacturing industries such as aerospace and automotive.

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy-efficient and fast manufacturing of thermoset polymer composites is critical for next generation high-performance materials in aerospace, transportation, marine, and energy industries [1–4]. However, conventional curing methods for thermoset polymers, such as epoxy resins, use large ovens or autoclaves for curing cycles which take many hours, requiring a significant amount of energy and time [5,6]. Here, we use frontal ring-opening metathesis polymerization (FROMP) as a promising fast, energy-efficient curing method to produce carbon-fiber-reinforced poly-dicyclopentadiene. This curing reaction is driven by the exothermic heat generated during the polymerization of the DCPD monomer in the presence of Grubbs catalyst. In the FROMP process, the exothermic reaction is spatially localized near a propagating front, which is triggered thermally at one starting location, enabling fast and low-energy manufacturing [5,7]. In composites, the front can propagate longitudinally along the fibers, or through the thickness if triggered by heat from a heated mold brought in contact with the surface of the composite. However, if insufficient energy is present at the front, for instance due to heat loss to the surrounding or fast heat conduction ahead of the front by the carbon fibers, undesired front quenching might occur [8,9]. For this reason, through-thickness curing is often preferred when large volume fraction composites are desired, as quenching is avoided with through-thickness curing [10,11]. Therefore, it is important to investigate an optimized thermal heating profile that fully cures the polymer with the desired curing time and energy simultaneously. To achieve this, understanding of the curing behavior in response to different thermal trigger profiles through theoretical and numerical modeling of FROMP is essential.

In this study, we develop a numerical optimization process for the cyclic through-thickness FROMP curing of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites to realize rapid and low-energy manufacturing of large composites. The cyclic curing enables the use of a small footprint oven to cure large area composites by cyclic feeding and through-thickness front curing in a stepped manner. Due to the exothermic heat generation, continuous external thermal energy supply throughout the process is unnecessary, allowing for various curing profiles depending on the heating method. Furthermore, in the repeated FROMP processes, changes in the initial conditions for subsequent cycles due to high-temperature regions from previous cycles require additional analysis for an optimized thermal management cycle. To address these issues, computational models considering thermo-chemical reaction-diffusion equations are utilized, providing insights into FROMP. In addition, a combination of numerical modeling and experimental validation can further enhance the reliability of FROMP manufacturing.

As shown in Figures 1(a) and 1(b), we model the frontal polymerization of CFRP and apply a gradient-based optimization process to derive an optimized low-energy-consuming heating cycle. For the modeling, we consider three different domains: heater, CFRP, and insulator. DCPD and carbon fiber are used as monomer and reinforcement in the CFRP for reaction-diffusion analysis. The simulation allows us to derive temperature changes and degree of cure variations in the domains with different heating power profiles, enabling the analysis of the impact of thermal management in cyclic curing processes. In the optimization stage, a parametric optimization algorithm is applied to the design variables (e.g., heating, cooling, feeding time, and heating power) to minimize energy consumption while achieving the desired process time and degree of cure conditions. Finally, through experiments, we analyze the curing results and demonstrate the incremental CFRP curing process of a long composite structure using a small footprint oven with lower energy consumption compared to conventional curing conditions by applying the heating cycle proposed by the model and algorithm, as shown in Figure 1(c). Based on the results obtained from this study, the optimized curing strategies can be applied to large-scale manufacturing processes by implementing energy-efficient, low-cost FROMP cycles. This result supports the advancement of sustainable manufacturing for high-performance thermoset polymers and composite materials in various applications.

Figure 1: Proposed computational and experimental study for thermal management optimization: (a) numerical modeling for reaction-diffusion equations and cure kinetics, (b) optimization process for the heating cycle, and (c) experiment to demonstrate the optimized FROMP process.

2 MODELING OF COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING

2.1 Reaction-diffusion equation for incremental curing model

For the FROMP-based incremental composite model, we develop a 1D transient finite element model implemented in the FEniCS open-source finite element framework. During the manufacturing process, an insulation layer and a heater domain are required to apply pressure to the composite and initiate through-thickness FROMP, respectively. Therefore, three domains including insulation, composite, and heater layers were applied for the simulation, as illustrated in Figure 2(a). To capture the exothermic reaction and heat transfer, reaction-diffusion relations and heat conduction equations in through-thickness direction (x) were applied, as shown in Equations (1)–(4)[7,12]. Specifically, a phenomenological $g(\alpha)$ model based on the Prout-Tompkins formulation[12] was used to describe the cure kinetics as follows:

$$\overline{\rho C_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \bar{k} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \rho_m (1 - \phi) H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

$$g(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \alpha^m \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(c_d(\alpha - \alpha_d))} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_i C_{p_i} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_i \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{\rho C_p}$ ($J/(m^3 K)$) is the homogenized volumetric heat capacity of the composite derived using the rule of mixtures, and \bar{k} ($W/(m K)$) is effective thermal conductivity of the composite. The temperature, time, matrix density, fiber volume fraction, enthalpy of the FROMP reaction, and degree of cure are denoted by $T(K)$, $t(s)$, $\rho_m(kg/m^3)$, ϕ , $H_r(365000 J/kg)$, and α respectively. Regarding Equation (2), time constant, activation energy, and universal gas constant are respectively denoted by $A(8.55e + 15 1/s)$, $E(110750 J/mol)$, $R(8.314 J/(mol K))$. In Equation (3), the constants used in the Prout-Tompkins model are given by $n = 1.72$, $m = 0.77$, $c_d = 14.48$, and $\alpha_d = 0.41$. Since no curing reaction occurs in the insulation ($i = 1$) and heater ($i = 2$) domains, only Equation (4) is applied to those regions. Other material properties used in the simulation are summarized in Table 1[7].

Figure 2: (a) Simulation geometry for incremental curing model, and (b) example of applied heat flux over time for initiation frontal polymerization in composite manufacturing

		Thermal conductivity ($W/(m K)$)	Density (kg/m^3)	Specific heat ($J/(kgK)$)
Carbon fiber	DCPD	0.15	980	1600
	AS4	10.45	1760	795
Insulation	PTFE	0.03	2200	970
	Calcium silicate	0.10	232.27	840
Heater	PI	0.12	1420	1090
	Silicone rubber	0.3	1200	1100

Table 1: Material properties of carbon fiber, insulation, and heater

For the incremental curing process, a heat flux profile $q_1(t)$ is applied in the first cycle to initiate the curing reaction in the CFRP. After the initial CFRP section is cured, a new uncured CFRP is fed into the system, and the second curing cycle begins with a heat flux profile of $q_2(t)$. This process is repeated for multiple curing cycles (see Figure 2(a)). Notably, due to residual heat from the previous cycle, the insulation and heater domains are preheated, which allows the subsequent curing cycle to achieve a fully cured result with a reduced energy input. Figure 2(b) shows examples of the applied heat flux profiles used to initiate the first curing cycle. In all simulations, the initial conditions were set as $\alpha_0 = 0.01$ and $T_0 = 20^\circ C$.

2.2 Curing behavior under different thermal conditions

As shown in Figure 2(b), the area under the heat flux-time plots represents the energy input per unit area (J/m^2). In these examples, the applied surface energy inputs for three different cases (i.e., profiles of q , $q/2$, and $q/4$) are 724.3, 362.1, and 181.1 kJ/m^2 , respectively. By using these thermal boundary conditions in the curing system, spatiotemporal distributions of temperature and degree of cure under three different curing conditions were obtained. The x -axis represents time, while the y -axis indicates spatial position through the three domains (heater, composite, and insulation), allowing observation of the temperature and cure distribution across each layer.

The thickness values of the heater, composite, and insulation layers are set to 1, 2.2, and 25.4 mm, respectively. In addition, the materials are applied as silicone, rubber, DCPD/AS4 with a fiber volume fraction of 0.65, and PTFE, respectively. We use spatiotemporal plots as a representation of the temperature evolution, represented by colored contours, along the 1-D domain during the curing as shown in Figure 3. We also construct similar contour plots for the degree-of-cure. This type of plot represents the evolution in space and time and hence a single plot replaces a 1-D movie of the curing process, obtained via numerical simulations. As shown in Figures 3(a) and 3(d), the curing is initiated

near the heater and propagates through the composite toward the insulation layer. The degree of cure eventually reaches ~ 0.98 , indicating that full cure is achieved. Assuming 0.95 as the threshold for complete cure, this result suggests that cure time and energy input can be further optimized using a slightly lower heat flux or shorter heating duration.

On the other hand, Figures 3(b) and 3(e) show that while the FROMP is initiated with a reduced energy input, it cannot sustain propagation due to heat loss to surrounding domains, resulting in incomplete cure. Furthermore, in Figures 3(c) and 3(f), the supplied energy is insufficient even for the initiation of FROMP, and the degree of cure at the end of the composite remains at 0.23. These results highlight the importance of proper thermal management (heat flux and heating duration) to ensure complete and energy-efficient curing of composite materials.

Figure 3: Saptiotemporal simulation results of temperature and degree of cure under different thermal trigger conditions: temperature distributions for (a) q , (b) $q/2$, and (c) $q/4$, and degree of cure distributions for (d) q , (e) $q/2$, and (f) $q/4$

2.3 Thermal cycle optimization

Figure 4(a) presents the results of a parametric study in which random constant heat flux values (q_h) and heating durations (t_h) are applied. For each case where the degree of cure at the end of the composite (through-thickness direction) reaches 0.95, the required time is defined as the curing time (t_c). The corresponding energy input is calculated based on a surface area of 0.012 m^2 . Two cases are considered for comparison. For Case 1, heat flux is applied continuously until the composite is fully cured ($t_h = t_c$), while heat flux is terminated earlier ($t_h < t_c$), allowing the remaining cure to proceed through exothermic FROMP reaction in Case 2. These two cases are shown in different colors in Figure 4(a). As a result, a clear distinction between the two cases is identified. Overall, Case 1 uses more energy than Case 2, indicating that FROMP-based composite manufacturing can be significantly more energy-efficient. For instance, comparing the data points highlighted with green dashed lines, both cases require similar curing times, but Case 2 achieves approximately 22.12% energy savings compared to Case 1.

In addition, Case 2 demonstrates a trade-off relationship between curing time and energy input. Achieving shorter curing time requires more energy consumption, whereas longer curing time leads to lower energy input during the curing cycle. To further explore this relationship, a genetic algorithm (GA) is employed to minimize the energy consumption. The optimization result shows that compared to Case 1, energy consumption can be reduced by 33.27%, although the corresponding curing time increases from 87 to 296 s. Therefore, by evaluating a wide range of conditions, a Pareto front can be identified to balance both energy and curing time, providing guidance for the thermal profile design of the first

cycle. Moreover, since the surrounding domains are preheated by the previous cycle, subsequent cycles require less energy input. As illustrated in Figure 4(b), this concept is applied by scaling down the heat flux in the following cycles to achieve incremental curing with reduced energy input.

Figure 4: (a) Fully cured state and corresponding thermal conditions of curing time and supplied energy. (b) Numerical approach for determining the optimized incremental curing thermal cycle.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

3.1 Materials

For the resin system, DCPD, which is solid at room temperature, is mixed with 5 wt% ethylidene norbornene (ENB) to liquify it at room temperature and enable infusion into the carbon fibers. We refer to this mixture as DCPD in the following formulation. A molar ratio of 10000:1:1 of DCPD, second-generation Grubbs catalyst (GC2), and tributyl phosphite (TBP) was mixed using sonication to ensure uniform dispersion. For the carbon fiber layup, an AS4 carbon fiber fabric with the stacking sequence of unidirectional/biaxial/biaxial/unidirectional was used. The prepared resin was then infiltrated into the fabric preform, which was sealed in a nylon vacuum bag. To prevent premature curing at room temperature, the prepregs were stored in a freezer prior to the curing process.

3.2 Experimental setup

Figure 5(a) shows the experimental setup used to validate the optimized curing process. The temperature profiles of the heater and the composite were derived from the optimized heat flux-based thermal profile. To implement this, a K-type thermocouple and a high-sampling-rate PID controller were employed. In addition, an actuator and a calcium silicate insulation layer were used to apply a pressure of ~35 psi. Furthermore, a spring stage and microswitch were introduced to monitor and maintain consistent pressure during all curing cycles. The pressure was controlled by the displacement of the mechanical springs supporting the lower tooling plate as shown in Figure 5. An infrared camera was used to monitor the temperature of the entire system and ensure consistent initial thermal conditions.

Figure 5: (a) Experimental setup for through-thickness frontal polymerization-based composite manufacturing. (b) Temperature results of three curing cycles based on the optimized curing profile

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We selected the experimental validation conditions from the Pareto front data points obtained from the simulations of the thermal profile parameters of heat flux (q_h) and heating time (t_h). Specifically, we selected 15267 W/m^2 and 41 s as the optimized thermal cycle for the first section, respectively. In addition, based on the simulation, the expected curing time (t_c) was 61 s for a single curing segment. For the following curing cycles, a scale factor of 0.56 was applied to the heating profile based on numerical fitting for the experimental validation. As shown in Figure 5(b), the intended temperature profiles were successfully applied in each curing section through precise PID control. Notably, the proposed curing cycle required only 61 s per cycle, and a composite panel of $228.6 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$ was successfully fabricated using only 3 min and 5.05 kJ of energy.

Figure 6 presents optical images and the thermomechanical analysis of the incrementally cured composite. Before the curing process, the resin remained in a liquid state, as observed in the uncured regions, seen in Figure 6(a). The cured composite was characterized via 3-point bend dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). As shown in Figure 6(b), the cured composite exhibited a storage modulus onset glass transition temperature (T_g) of $148 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which are comparable to previously reported values for fully cured systems [7,10]. These results experimentally validate the thermal profile derived from the proposed numerical approach and demonstrate its potential applicability for large-scale incremental composite curing.

Figure 6: Composite curing using low energy and rapid curing cycle. (a) Optical images of composite before and after curing. (b) DMA test results of the cured composite.

5 CONCLUSION

In this work, the optimization of a FROMP-based incremental composite curing process was investigated numerically and experimentally towards enabling rapid and energy-efficient manufacturing. Through numerical simulations, various heating conditions were explored to find the Pareto front representing the trade-off between energy consumption and total curing time. Subsequently, an optimized first curing cycle condition was selected and extended to multiple curing cycles. In addition, the obtained curing cycle for the incremental curing was validated through experimental method. In conclusion, a 228.6 mm × 50 mm composite with a high glass transition temperature of 148 °C was successfully fabricated using only 5.05 kJ of energy in 3 min. The proposed approach demonstrates potential for scalable, rapid, and energy-efficient manufacturing of fiber-reinforced composites, specifically for applications in aerospace, space, and the automotive industry.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Traiforos N, Turner T, Runeberg P, Fernass D, Chronopoulos D, Glock F, et al. A simulation framework for predicting process-induced distortions for precise manufacturing of aerospace thermoset composites. *Compos Struct* 2021;275:114465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.114465>.
- [2] Zhang Z, Liu R, Li W, Liu Y, Luo H, Zeng L, et al. Direct writing of continuous carbon fibers/epoxy thermoset composites with high-strength and low energy-consumption. *Addit Manuf* 2021;47:102348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102348>.
- [3] Abouhamzeh M, Sinke J. Effects of fusion bonding on the thermoset composite. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2019;118:142–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.12.031>.
- [4] Crawford S, Lungu CT. Influence of temperature on styrene emission from a vinyl ester resin thermoset composite material. *Science of The Total Environment* 2011;409:3403–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.05.042>.
- [5] Robertson ID, Yourdkhani M, Centellas PJ, Aw JE, Ivanoff DG, Goli E, et al. Rapid energy-efficient manufacturing of polymers and composites via frontal polymerization. *Nature* 2018;557:223–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0054-x>.
- [6] Timmis AJ, Hodzic A, Koh L, Bonner M, Soutis C, Schäfer AW, et al. Environmental impact assessment of aviation emission reduction through the implementation of composite materials. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 2015;20:233–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-014-0824-0>.
- [7] Vyas S, Parikh NA, Price TC, Patel DP, Le TB, Geubelle PH, et al. Through-thickness frontal polymerization: Process development and optimization. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2024;180:108084. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108084>.
- [8] Suslick BA, Hemmer J, Groce BR, Stawiasz KJ, Geubelle PH, Malucelli G, et al. Frontal polymerizations: From chemical perspectives to macroscopic properties and applications. *Chem Rev* 2023;123:3237–98. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00686>.
- [9] Goli E, Gai T, Geubelle PH. Impact of boundary heat losses on frontal polymerization. *J Phys Chem B* 2020;124:6404–11. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpccb.0c03107>.

- [10] Abdullah AM, Zakoworotny M, Zhang C, Geubelle PH, Baur JW. Rapid out-of-oven lamination (ROL) for energy-efficient manufacturing of carbon fiber reinforced composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2025;194:108873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2025.108873>.
- [11] Hmeidat NS, Zakoworotny M, Kim YS, Le TB, DeBrun G, Shah R, et al. Reactive extrusion of frontally polymerizing continuous carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2025;190:108609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108609>.
- [12] Goli E, Parikh NA, Yourdkhani M, Hibbard NG, Moore JS, Sottos NR, et al. Frontal polymerization of unidirectional carbon-fiber-reinforced composites. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2020;130:105689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.105689>.